

Cybersecurity in Hospital Digitalization: Economic Implications and Financing Strategies

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Abstract

The digital revolution has brought significant benefits to healthcare services, including data management, increased operational efficiency, and innovation in various areas of patient services. The impact of this digitalization not only brings benefits but also creates recent problems that must be faced by each healthcare facility, one of which is cyber-attacks. Cybersecurity is a top priority to address threats to hospital systems and patient data. It takes around USD 7 million per incident to restore the system caused by a cyber-attack. An urgent need needs to be done to improve cybersecurity measures in all areas, including the healthcare sector. Weak cybersecurity can cause delays in services, operations, decreased reputation, and financial burdens for hospitals. To overcome this problem, a special budget needs to be allocated by hospitals for system updates and maintenance, staff training, and to procure tools that support cybersecurity. Innovative financing approaches need to be taken such as utilizing AI-based systems, insurance for cybersecurity, and collaborating partnerships between the public and private sector in supporting cybersecurity. Staff training programs and regular cybersecurity audits are also considered necessary because they can increase resilience to potential cyberattacks. Effective cybersecurity is a reflection of the success of digitalization in hospitals. Good budget management to support the establishment of a

cyber security system has an impact on protecting hospital systems and patient data security.

Keywords: cyber security, economic implications, financing strategies.

Introduction

The development of technology and information on a global scale is progressing at an unprecedented pace, with the digital era permeating all aspects of people's lives. Health services, including hospitals and other health facilities, are not immune from this transformation. Hospital digitalization is an obligation stipulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. 82 of 2013 concerning hospital management information systems. This system covers all aspects of hospital operations, integrating them into a network structure, helping data coordination, reporting, and administrative procedures. The goal is to ensure the acquisition of appropriate and accurate data(1). Strategic implementation of technological solutions in health care settings is essential, as it facilitates improved data and information quality, optimization of service delivery, reduction of clinical errors, reduction of data redundancy, and acceleration of patient data access(2).

The emergence of hospital digitization has provided many benefits and conveniences, but at the same time it has also given rise to new challenges and problems. One of them is the vulnerability of health data security. According to the 2020 Global Cyber Security Index (GCI), Indonesia is ranked 24th in terms of cybersecurity (3). Given the increasingly widespread threat of cyber-attacks, this issue must be considered in the context of hospital digitization. The impact of cybercrime not only directly affects health workers who face challenges in accessing and retrieving important health information, but often requires large financial investments to fix these problems. The need for strong cybersecurity is essential in ensuring the safety and trust of patients, who should feel protected from the potential loss of their personal data.

Health data security is a fundamental human right, and its protection is therefore of utmost importance. Cybersecurity is a critical part of this effort, as it involves implementing measures designed to protect patient data from potential cyber threats. These measures include securing networks, devices, and data from unauthorized access or illegal use(4). The overall goal of cybersecurity is to ensure the privacy, accessibility, and integrity of information transmitted over the internet. In the context of healthcare facilities, cybersecurity plays a critical role in ensuring the security of patient health data, thereby preventing misuse by irresponsible parties.

The importance of cybersecurity requires significant financial resources, which in turn affects the economic and financial dimensions of healthcare institutions. Large-scale hospital operations undeniably demand effective economic strategies and management to ensure the implementation of robust cybersecurity measures. This is a significant challenge in hospital digitalization and is closely related to the economic and financial aspects of healthcare institutions.

Discussion

Digital transformation in hospitals has a positive impact on services and lightens the burden on health workers. The use of digitalization in hospitals based on technology and information is in fact inseparable from lurking cybercrime. Hospitals are faced with cyber challenges due to weak security.

1. Cybersecurity challenges in hospitals

Cybersecurity in hospitals is a challenge in hospital management. The cybersecurity challenges are(5):

- a. There is an increasing threat of attacks where hospitals are becoming easy targets for hackers who try to access medical data and damage hospital IT infrastructure.
- b. The complexity of IT infrastructure that connects medical devices and patient data. Where all of them are interconnected with the interdependent

hospital management system, the vulnerability to cyber threats is extremely high.

- c. The need for protection of patient medical data that includes personal data that has been stored in an electronic system. Where if the data is leaked it can cause losses both financially, legally, and reputationally for the agency.
- d. Regulations related to the protection of patient personal data must meet strict standards and regulations such as the ITE Law.

2. Economic implications and cybersecurity

Disruption due to cyber-attacks on the hospital environment has a major impact. Weak cyber security is certainly easy to hack by criminals. This also has an impact on the hospital's economic management, especially in the use of operational funds. The things that affect the economic impact of cyber security threats are:

a. Recovery costs from cyber attacks

For hospitals that are victims of cyber-attacks, they are faced with huge costs to restore the system. There are even some devices that are damaged with large losses. Cyber-attacks are financially detrimental where large funds are needed to restore hospital and patient data. A single incident of hospital breach can cost up to USD 7 million including fines, litigation, and reputational damage(6). Hospitals need added funds for system recovery, cybersecurity enhancements, software updates, and employee training.

b. Operational disruption

The impact of the cyber-attack that occurred had an impact on hospital services. Several services such as patient examinations, delays in medical procedures, and reduced staff productivity were disrupted. This certainly had an impact on the income of the hospital, which was forced to temporarily stop services. Another more important disruption is that it can endanger the safety of patients who need special treatment(7).

c. Agency reputation

Data leaks due to weak cybersecurity can damage public trust in hospitals. This loss of reputation results in a decrease in the number of patients which affects hospital revenue. In addition, a bad reputation affects cooperative relationships with business partners and insurance providers.

3. Financing strategies for cybersecurity

a. Dedicated funding allocation and cybersecurity investment

The importance of distributing a specific budget in financial planning every year. The budget is used for investments in cybersecurity such as staff training, audits, periodic equipment maintenance, both purchasing software and upgrading IT infrastructure(8).

b. Cyber security insurance

Proper fund allocation is like investing in an insurance policy that specifically covers losses from cyber incidents. The insurance policy covers data recovery costs, legal fines, and revenue losses due to operational disruptions. This can reduce the financial burden on hospitals due to cyber-attacks(9).

c. Utilization of government funds and grants

Funding from the government and private institutions that provide grants or subsidized loans supports hospitals in economic management, especially for strengthening cybersecurity and other IT infrastructure.

d. Education and training for employees and staff

Human resources are one of the important points in strengthening cyber security. Training programs are needed to improve staff competence and awareness of cyber threats so that they can prevent data hacking. Competent staff are at the forefront of dealing with cyber-attacks. Training includes attack simulations, phishing, regular updates on the latest threats, and the importance of emphasizing security practices in daily activities(10).

e. Private institutional partnership

Partnering with a technology company that provides cybersecurity services can provide access and support resources and ability that are not available internally. Hospitals can collaborate with partners in managing cyber threats in the health sector. This partnership can take the form of consulting services, training programs and collaborations that can help hospitals stay *up to date* with the latest cyber threats (11).

f. Periodic security audits

Hospitals need to conduct regular audits to ensure that everything is running smoothly and securely. Audits include checking hardware, software, and operational practices. Audits can be used as a basis for cybersecurity strategies and ensure that hospitals are safe and ready in case of a cyber threat.

4. Innovative opportunities for financing

Innovating in hospital cybersecurity financing can be done in several ways as follows.

a. AI-based investment

Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be a solution for hospitals in detecting and preventing cyber threats automatically. AI technology can be a high investment that can reduce long-term operational burdens(12).

b. Crowdfunding and Public Campaigns

The use of crowdfunding platforms can be used to raise funds from the community and community partners. Hospitals can get cash injections from the results of these services.

c. Collaboration with Subscription on Technology Startups

In this digital era, there are many technology companies that provide security services with sophisticated systems that they have. Hospitals need to collaborate with startup companies by adopting a subscription-based model. With collaboration, they can provide access to sophisticated technology at an affordable price every month.

Conclusion

Hospital digitalization in its management requires security for important patients and hospital data. Cyber-attacks not only threaten personal data but also cause economic effects in operations and harm the hospital's reputation. The threats that come cannot be predicted so prevention and cyber security are needed. Special fund allocations, partnerships between government and private institutions, cyber insurance, and other financing innovations are needed that can help hospitals deal with cyber-attacks.

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